

Navigating Abstract Timbre Spaces: Instrumental Affordances of Concatenative Synthesis in Mosaïque

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Abstract

This paper explores how accessible tools for corpus-based concatenative synthesis—specifically the Mosaïque software—enable new modes of musical practice by placing artists at the center of real-time sound exploration. Mosaïque democratizes this synthesis method by allowing users—including those with no coding experience—to build and navigate sound corpora in spatialized timbre environments shaped by perceptual descriptors and dimensionality reduction. Emphasizing gesture, improvisation, and listening, the software fosters a practice rooted in embodied interaction and intuitive control. Using a research-creation methodology, we examine how musicians engage with Mosaïque as both instrument and interface. We focus on three key creative areas: corpus creation, timbral navigation and sound design opportunities. Through case studies and first-person accounts, we analyze how artists shape and are shaped by this technology, developing sensorimotor fluency, exploring collective creativity through shared corpora, and challenging conventional compositional paradigms. Situated within electroacoustic theory, human-computer interaction, and creative AI frameworks, we argue that tools like Mosaïque foster inclusive and exploratory musicking practices.

1 Context of research creation

Corpus-based concatenative synthesis (CBCS)—a technique involving the assembly of short audio fragments drawn from a large corpus—emerges from a lineage of sound manipulation rooted in sampling practices (Bernardes et al., 2013). It has been applied in a variety of experimental and electroacoustic music contexts, including composition, improvisation, and performance (Einbond et al., 2016; Ghisi, 2017; Schwarz, 2012). The formalization of the term in a musical context is credited to Diemo Schwarz (2006), whose foundational work at IRCAM, including CataRT (Schwarz, 2006b) and SkataRT, established core methodologies for real-time corpus exploration.

This research is also informed by more recent projects that emphasize accessibility and community-oriented tool development (Tremblay et al., 2019). The FluCoMa project (Tremblay et al., 2021) has been instrumental in sharing advanced analysis tools with a broad user base, fostering

pedagogical and creative engagement. Its open-source libraries are extensively used in the development of Mosaïque, our own concatenative synthesizer. Similarly, the SP Tools (Constanzo, 2022) and the intuitive design of AudioStellar (Garber & Ciccola, 2021) offer distinct yet complementary approaches to corpus-based sound interaction, underscoring the field’s growing diversity.

The organization of sound corpora for musical reuse has long been a theme in electroacoustic practice. With the advent of powerful digital tools and real-time processing, these strategies have evolved into more systematic and accessible forms. Environments such as Max, Pure Data, and SuperCollider have played a crucial role in democratizing CBCS by enabling experimentation with segmentation, feature extraction, and dynamic sound selection.

More than a technical process, CBCS represents a conceptual shift in how musicians engage with sonic materiality. Rather than reproducing or transforming isolated samples, artists explore timbre as a navigable space—what has come to be known as “timbre space.” (Bell, 2023) Here, audio fragments are positioned in multidimensional proximity based on perceptual similarity, allowing users to traverse a sonic topology through performance or algorithmic control (Roma et al., 2019). This model opens new possibilities for interaction, composition, and real-time improvisation.

1.1 Problematics

While the possibilities of corpus-based concatenative synthesis have expanded dramatically with the availability of real-time audio analysis and dimensionality reduction algorithms, a gap persists between the technical sophistication of these tools and their accessibility to the wider musical community. Our experience in digital music pedagogy has shown that many existing platforms still demand a high degree of technical knowledge, limiting the creative potential for those without programming experience. The literature indicates that using CBCS requires musicians to understand several new concepts that are not part of current musical training in the electroacoustic music curriculum¹.

The challenge, then, is not only technological but conceptual and pedagogical. How can we foster familiarity and fluency with these new instruments based on CBCS? What kinds of aesthetic and musical practices emerge when timbre becomes the primary medium of interaction? And how can tools like Mosaïque support an inclusive community of users—from novices to experts—by foregrounding embodied experience, improvisation, and curiosity as the basis for musicking?

From an aesthetic perspective, CBCS enables the exploration of sound corpora in a virtual timbre space shaped by perceptual similarity. This also raises questions regarding the forms of musical understanding that may arise when sound is conceptualized not as a linear progression, but as a spatial terrain to be navigated. How do such environments change the way musicians conceptualize instruments and “musicking”?

1.2 Theoretical framework

This research sits at the intersection of electroacoustic music, human-computer interaction (HCI), and creative artificial intelligence (AI), drawing on multiple theoretical perspectives to articulate how Mosaïque reshapes compositional practice through corpus-based concatenative synthesis.

1.2.1 Electroacoustic and Computer Music Theory

Foundational work by Barry Truax (1990) and Curtis Roads (2001) on granular and corpus-based synthesis informs the conceptual basis of Mosaïque, especially in exploring new modes of sonic organization. Pierre Schaeffer’s (1966) theory of *musique concrète* and Denis Smalley’s (1997) spectromorphology offer analytical tools for understanding how users perceive and structure sound corpora. These perspectives enable a phenomenological reading of sonic material as performative, mediated, and organized through listening. Demers (2010) expands this phenomenological view by exploring how experimental electronic music aesthetics often displace formal or referential meaning in favor of direct engagement with sonic texture and process.

¹ The FluCoMa project has identified similar pedagogical concerns and has published resources to help with the formation of the community <https://github.com/flucoma/flucoma-for-pedagogues/blob/main/flucoma-for-pedagogues.pdf>

1.2.2 Human-Computer Interaction and Digital Instrument Design

Mosaïque is conceived not only as a tool but as a digital musical instrument (Jordà, 2005), where interface design, affordances, and feedback mechanisms shape artistic outcomes. Research on gestural interaction (Miranda & Wanderley, 2006) highlights the embodied nature of performing in timbre space. Fiebrink's Wekinator (Fiebrink & Sonami, 2020) exemplifies how real-time machine learning can support expressive mapping between gesture and sound. Schwarz (2012) argues that in CBCS, the instrument is not the playback device but the timbre space itself—an interactive sonic landscape that musicians navigate through gesture. This conceptualization frames the interface not just as a control surface but as a site of musical embodiment and performance.

1.2.3 Creativity, Cognition, and Learning

Navigating complex timbre spaces engages embodied knowledge, memory, and intuitive exploration. This aligns with theories of embodied cognition (Leman, 2012) and sensorimotor learning (Bevilacqua et al., 2016), positioning Mosaïque as a site where musical fluency develops through iterative, performative interaction.

1.2.4 Machine Listening and Creative AI

Mosaïque participates in ongoing discourse around machine listening and computational creativity by putting forward machine listening and learning through audio feature extraction and dimensionality reduction techniques. By mapping high-dimensional descriptors into 2D or 3D spaces, Mosaïque foregrounds abstraction, representation, and exploratory design, while raising questions about artist-agency in opaque AI systems, as described by Manovich (2018).

Together, these domains frame Mosaïque as a hybrid instrument-environment that enables new modes of composition, interaction, and listening—where creative AI is not just a generator of content, but a mediator of exploratory musical engagement.

1.3 Methodology

This study adopts a research-creation methodology, where artistic practice functions as both subject and method (Chapman & Sawchuk, 2015). Grounded in the belief that knowledge can emerge through creative activity, this approach intertwines theory, practice, and reflection. Our research developed through iterative engagement with Mosaïque, encompassing compositional experimentation, interface design, and pedagogical use.

The article reflects the team's documented discussions and reflections throughout the development and use of CBCS. The creation of Mosaïque itself became a means of deepening our understanding of the technique, translating creative insight into software features. This process was inspired by inductive methodologies such as the SampleRRN project at Manchester Conservatory (Ma et al., 2024)

Central to this approach is practice-based investigation. Artistic experimentation—corpus creation, playback design, and live performance—generated both aesthetic outcomes and critical questions. While not structured as formal case studies, our reflections are grounded in the creation of several musical works. These include *Navigating Calmer Oceans*, an improvised piece by the duo Tout Croche (Thibault & Harvey, 2024) developed for the Sound/Image Festival in Greenwich (UK); *Topologies d'intrication* by David Piazza (2025), in which multiple instances of Mosaïque respond dynamically to a Buchla synthesizer; and *Stella's Prophet* by João Catalão and Dominic Thibault, (2024) which stages a modal improvisation between a vibraphone and Mosaïque. Authors Allard, Arseneault and Moriceau are also in the process of composing musical pieces using Mosaïque as we write these lines. These acts were not supplementary but served as our primary investigative lens, allowing users to develop a nuanced understanding of the software's expressive affordances.

The methodology also embraces heuristic processes: trial and error, intuition, and embodied feedback guided tool refinement and artistic evolution. This iterative cycle mirrors the navigation-driven nature of CBCS and privileges subjective experience as a source of insight. As Zappi & McPherson (2014) note, the process of learning a digital instrument involves both adapting to its structural constraints and discovering expressive potentials, a trajectory that closely aligns with our use and development of Mosaïque.

Pedagogical implementation forms a complementary axis. In workshops and classroom settings, Mosaïque provided a platform for observing how learners engage with timbral space. These contexts revealed diverse strategies for navigation and sound manipulation, offering a window into how musical intuition and technical skills develop together.

Finally, we analyzed user practices and artistic outcomes to articulate how Mosaïque enables new modes of musicking. By integrating artistic creation, user experience, and theoretical reflection, this methodology offers a multifaceted view of how CBCS can reshape musical processes.

2 Understanding the tool: *Mosaïque*

Figure 1 Graphical interface of the Mosaïque Max for Live device

Mosaïque (see Figure 1 Graphical interface of the Mosaïque Max for Live device) is a user-friendly software environment for corpus-based concatenative synthesis, introduced to the community in 2024 (Thibault, 2024). Implemented as a Max for Live device, it enables users to explore and manipulate large collections of sounds—corpora—through an interactive visual interface. Each instance can host up to eight corpora composed of audio slices extracted from individual files or long recordings processed by Mosaïque’s built-in slicer.

Once loaded, the sounds are analyzed using a set of audio descriptors and projected into a three-dimensional timbre space via dimensionality reduction techniques (see Figure 2). Users can navigate this space using the Viewer or through various gestural interfaces, enabling real-time control of sound selection based on spatial positioning. All controls are mappable and automatable, facilitating both exploratory and performance-based workflows.

Figure 2 Examples of 3D representations of the corpora in Mosaïque

A dedicated playback section provides parameters for polyphony, looping, speed, pitch, and envelope shaping. These controls support nuanced sound design and real-time manipulation. Users can save and recall corpora along with their spatial mappings, allowing for long-term engagement with sound materials and the sharing of presets between users, thereby fostering collaborative creative practices.

Mosaïque’s server–client architecture allows the timbre space to be accessed simultaneously by multiple players, supporting polyphonic triggering across different timbral regions. This setup positions Mosaïque as both an instrument and a compositional environment, where sonic behavior can be shaped in layered and coordinated ways.

The system includes several playback engines—or "players"—each offering unique temporal and textural characteristics. These include granular, morphing, and freeze modes, expanding the expressive range and supporting a wide variety of performance strategies.

3.3 Creative practices observations

This section presents key modes of creative engagement enabled by corpus-based concatenative synthesis in *Mosaïque*. Drawing on artistic, technical, and pedagogical practice, we highlight three interconnected dimensions: corpus construction, gestural navigation of timbre space and sound design opportunities. Each illustrates how *Mosaïque* fosters new forms of musical exploration.

3.1 Corpus creation and dataset curation

Creating an effective corpus is central to corpus-based concatenative synthesis. Since the corpus constitutes the sandbox from which the instrument draws its sonic material, the careful curation and organization of that corpus directly shape the aesthetic and expressive potential of the system. Although the process may appear technical (see Figure 3), it is inherently exploratory, creative, and iterative. Artists often require time and repeated engagement with the process before developing a strong intuition about how to structure, slice, and organize sound material effectively. With experience, users begin to perceive their corpora as instruments in their own right—structures that embed compositional ideas and afford rich opportunities for interaction.

Figure 3 Pipeline of the corpora importation in *Mosaïque*

3.1.1 Collecting musical datasets

The process of collecting audio material for a corpus often involves a balance between artistic intent and sonic exploration. This stage is rarely formulaic; rather, it relies on experimentation and iterative refinement. Artists report that the selection of material is guided by a search for meaningful relationships among sounds—tonal compatibility, textural contrast, and narrative potential are all considered.

The types of sound that can be incorporated into a corpus are as diverse as the creative visions that drive them. These may include:

- Field recordings or soundscapes from natural and urban environments,
- Archival voice recordings, foley effects, or spoken text,
- Instrumental recordings (either solo or ensemble),
- Synthesized textures, drones, rhythmic loops, or harmonic beds.

Each corpus carries a latent conceptual dimension—supporting narrativity, evoking place or memory, or offering affordances for performance.

For example, in *Un ouvrage sans fin*, *Mosaïque* was used to create a sonic memory system from vocal and gestural recordings by dramaturge Daniel Danis. Arranged within timbre space, the material formed a spatialized archive that visitors could explore to engage with memory through sound.

In *Stella's Prophet*, a reinterpretation of Victor Young's *Stella by Starlight*, a corpus of Prophet 6 synthesizer improvisations by João Catalão was segmented and loaded into *Mosaïque*. This became the basis for live performance, enabling real-time dialogue with Catalão's vibraphone. These examples demonstrate the artistic and pedagogical range of corpus creation.

3.1.2 Creative slicing

Once a sound dataset is assembled, the next step is to segment it into smaller slices for use in the concatenative synthesis engine. Though seemingly procedural, this step is deeply creative. Artists often work with long audio sequences, dividing them into fragments of varied length and timbral content to reflect the full richness of the source material.

While algorithmic tools assist with slicing, they often fall short of matching perceptual thresholds. As a result, practitioners refine parameters through experimentation and critical listening, developing a nuanced sense of how to shape their corpora to support expressive goals.

In practice, many users vary slice duration deliberately to enhance a sense of movement. Instead of relying solely on short segments, they retain or create longer slices that contrast with more active ones. This variation contributes to a more fluid and dynamic output, encouraging real-time exploration of both temporal and textural possibilities.

3.1.3 Audio descriptors

By default, Mosaïque analyzes each audio slice using a relatively extensive set of audio descriptors. Based on our experience, this feature set effectively captures salient aspects of timbre, as evidenced by the perceptually coherent spatial layouts produced within the timbre space. As such, we have rarely found it necessary to experiment with alternative descriptor configurations for creative purposes. Nevertheless, users who wish to customize the analysis process may do so via the interface (available under the cogwheel icon), where descriptor selection remains accessible for advanced exploration.

3.1.4 Abstract timbre spaces through dimensionality reduction

The shape and organization of timbre space in Mosaïque depend heavily on the algorithm used to project high-dimensional data into fewer dimensions—effectively determining the placement and size of mosaic tiles in the 3D environment.

When a corpus is imported, its audio slices are analyzed to produce high-dimensional feature datasets. These are then reduced—typically to 2D or 3D—for real-time exploration. Mosaïque uses the UMAP (Uniform Manifold Approximation and Projection) algorithm to generate a navigable projection of timbral similarity.

This transformation is not just technical—it defines the expressive and creative interface of the system. UMAP is well suited to this task, as it preserves both local and global relationships within the data. Crucially, UMAP’s parameters—such as number of neighbors, minimum distance, and iterations—directly affect how clusters are shaped, how distinct timbral regions appear, and how detailed internal relationships become. Thus, dimensionality reduction becomes an exploratory process, allowing users to shape the space to reflect perceptual or aesthetic goals.

Because UMAP is non-deterministic, each projection is unique—even with the same input. Navigation, therefore, is not about memorizing fixed layouts but developing sensitivity to emergent patterns. This invites a pedagogical process of sensorimotor learning, where users map their gestures to sonic outcomes over time.

As familiarity grows, performers begin to internalize the spatial structure of a corpus, developing individualized navigation strategies. This progression mirrors instrumental practice, where repeated engagement leads to embodied fluency. The timbre space becomes a tactile, playable surface—a dynamic extension of musical thought.

In this way, dimensionality reduction is more than a technical step; it is central to instrument building. It transforms a collection of fragments into a coherent, expressive interface shaped by both algorithm and performer.

3.1.5 Community sharing and collaboration

Mosaïque supports co-creativity through corpus sharing. Users can export and distribute their corpora, fostering a culture of exchange that enriches the broader creative community. This practice encourages knowledge transfer and pedagogical engagement, allowing users to study, adapt, and build on each other’s materials.

Shared corpora shift creation from an individual to a collective endeavor. Circulating these resources among peers contributes to a growing library of sonic material that reflects diverse aesthetics and techniques. In educational settings, this promotes collaborative learning and broadens students’ exposure to varied timbral vocabularies and structural strategies.

To support this, we provide a series of pre-analyzed corpora on our website², enabling immediate exploration. These materials serve as a bridge between first contact and more advanced usage, easing entry for beginners. After initial experimentation, learners often feel more confident in building personalized corpora, deepening their understanding of Mosaïque’s expressive possibilities.

This openness aligns with broader pedagogical goals: music technologies should foster inclusive creativity. Through corpus sharing, Mosaïque supports both individual expression and a participatory culture of exploration. These practices resonate with Chapman and Sawchuk’s (2015) ethnographic perspective on research-creation as a fundamentally collaborative process, where creative and scholarly knowledge is co-produced through communal engagement and shared tools.

3.2 Navigating the timbre space

Navigation within timbre space is central to creative practice in CBCS. In Mosaïque, this space is generated by analyzing the acoustic features of a corpus and projecting them into a lower-dimensional manifold, where perceptual similarity governs proximity: similar fragments cluster together, while contrasting ones are mapped further apart.

This space invites a shift in how we start musicking. Rather than layering discrete notes or rhythmic events, musicians move through a topological landscape, exploring continuous variations in timbre. Mosaïque emphasizes transition over juxtaposition—discovering how one sound flows into another rather than stacking them vertically. Navigation becomes a form of composition, where sonic gestures emerge as horizontal articulations akin to micro-montage.

In this paradigm, sounds unfold across trajectories—from harsh to soft, dense to sparse, large to small. Movement through timbre space becomes expressive in itself. The metaphor of navigation is apt: the user explores a sonic landscape, uncovering paths, territories, and transitions unique to each corpus. This aligns with Schwarz’s (2012) notion of the “sound space as a musical instrument,” in which expressive control emerges from navigating a topological projection of sonic descriptors. He emphasizes that such interaction becomes performative, especially when paired with gesture-sensitive controllers.

Yet this also presents a challenge: how can such movement be effectively accessed and controlled in real time or compositionally? This leads to questions about interface design, mapping strategies, and gestural affordances—all of which shape how musicians experience, learn, and perform with Mosaïque. What follows examines the methods and metaphors that support this engagement, and the expressive and pedagogical possibilities they afford.

3.2.1 Familiar musical paradigms

A key challenge in corpus-based concatenative synthesis is making the abstract timbre space accessible to musicians accustomed to conventional tools. Mosaïque addresses this by offering multiple interaction strategies grounded in familiar musical representations.

Users can control navigational coordinates—X, Y, and Z—corresponding to the timbre space dimensions. These parameters are fully mappable and automatable, allowing for both 2D and 3D interaction depending on the corpus and interface.

A common technique is mapping modulation sources like LFOs to spatial axes. For instance, an LFO controlling the X axis can introduce rhythmic movement, with its shape, speed, and depth shaping timbral transitions. More complex modulation can be achieved using generative agents or musical automata.

Mosaïque also integrates smoothly into MIDI-based workflows. Musicians can assign MIDI controllers to timbral dimensions, enabling gestural, real-time control. This reinforces an instrument-like experience where physical movement directly shapes sound. Automation curves provide precise, repeatable morphologies when needed.

Another key affordance is MIDI note triggering, which maps pitch to the X axis and velocity to Y. Identical pitch-velocity pairs recall the same slice; altering velocity selects a timbrally similar but

² <https://mosaique-en.cargo.site/corpora>

distinct fragment. This enables a balance of consistency and variation. Techniques like pitch shifts or velocity randomization expand expressive potential further.

These strategies help bridge the abstract nature of CBCS with tangible musical actions. By rooting navigation in familiar tools—modulation, MIDI control, automation—Mosaïque fosters intuitive interaction and empowers users to develop personal creative approaches.

3.2.2 Gestural interfaces

Beyond MIDI and modulation, Mosaïque supports gesture-based interaction, expanding its expressive and performative potential. These systems offer musicians the opportunity to develop embodied relationships with the timbre space, reinforcing the instrument-like qualities of CBCS.

Users can navigate corpora using normalized audio descriptors via a secondary pane, sorting fragments by features like brightness, loudness, or noisiness. This enables intuitive traversals—e.g., from dark to bright timbres or soft to intense textures.

Mosaïque also supports Open Sound Control (OSC), allowing integration with a broad range of gestural and custom controllers—including Leap Motion, the T-Stick, MediaPipe hand tracking, tablets, and Wacom devices. Graphic tablets, in particular, offer smooth, high-resolution control, enabling nuanced and continuous timbral transformations.

Because Mosaïque communicates via both MIDI and OSC, it is compatible with any commercial or DIY interface that transmits control data. Integration with Ableton’s Connection Kit and Max for Live tools further supports flexible performance setups, improvisation, and pedagogical use.

3.2.3 Audio mosaicking

Audio mosaicking is an emerging navigation strategy in Mosaïque that matches incoming audio to the closest timbral fragments in a corpus. The technique is explored extensively by Tremblay & Schwarz (2010), as they focus on the use of algorithms like KD-Tree nearest-neighbor search for low-latency response. Audio mosaicking enables the creation of hybrid timbral textures by dynamically responding to live or recorded input, blurring the boundary between source and corpus through evolving, layered morphologies.

However, the process can be complex. Mapping input descriptors to corpus content requires careful tuning and an understanding of descriptor spaces and emission rates, which can be a barrier for novice users. To address this, we are exploring a machine learning alternative: training a multi-layer perceptron (MLP) regressor to predict timbre space coordinates from incoming audio descriptors. While less precise, this method allows for creative and musically meaningful mappings, offering new avenues for expressive interaction. This reflects ideas developed by Zbyszyński et al. (Zbyszyński et al., 2021), who combine CBCS with regression-based mapping workflows to support expressive gestural control in high-dimensional feature spaces.

3.3 Sound design possibilities

3.3.1 Beyond granular synthesis

Corpus-based concatenative synthesis (CBCS) is often associated with granular synthesis (Joachim Gossmann & Max Neupert, 2014; Schwarz et al., 2016), as both involve triggering small audio units and producing textures reminiscent of granulation. Mosaïque, with its granular playback architecture, frequently invites this comparison from users.

However, this resemblance only hints at the broader creative potential of CBCS. We ask: can timbre spaces support other sampling paradigms—ones that go beyond dense snippet accumulation to enable controlled sampling, morphological shaping, and interactive performance? Mosaïque suggests that CBCS can evolve into a more nuanced and expressive sound design approach.

3.3.2 Sweeping sounds and morphological control

Mosaïque’s interface lends itself instinctively to what we call “sweeping sounds.” As the user moves their mouse or controller across the timbre space, clusters of sound fragments are triggered in rapid succession. These sonic agglomerations, inherently shaped by the layout of the feature space, become a defining aesthetic gesture within *Mosaïque*.

By default, each segment is triggered once per click, enabling users to design articulated sonic morphologies—fragments of precise length, controllable energy, and evolving spectral content. In *Stella's Prophet*, for example, *Mosaïque* is used to echo and extend vibraphone gestures, mirroring the phrasing and dynamics of the live instrument.

Importantly, sound is not produced passively; users must input energy into the system to activate the synthesis, echoing the interactive logic of acoustic instruments. This interactivity reinforces *Mosaïque's* potential as a performance-ready instrument rather than a static playback engine.

3.3.3 CBCS as Sampling Technique

To better understand the sound design possibilities of CBCS, it is useful to return to its fundamental nature: concatenative synthesis is a sampling technique. However, unlike traditional sampling, time is suppressed in favor of timbral organization. This shift in perspective opens the door to a variety of sample-based strategies.

By looping sound slices, adjusting pitch and speed, and defining the number of voices, users can accumulate sonic layers and sculpt dense polyphonies. *Mosaïque* makes it possible to improvise real-time orchestrations, or to structure compositions where each player assumes a role, playing back material with specific transformations.

3.3.4 Distributed architecture for sound design

Mosaïque's server–client architecture supports polyphonic and orchestral approaches by distributing analysis and playback across Ableton Live. Multiple clients can access distinct corpora—or segments of the same corpus—simultaneously, enabling layered playback with varied strategies applied to a single sound source.

The system includes several client types, each offering a distinct playback model:

- **Basic Player** replicates the server's core functions, allowing pitch, time, and envelope control with manual or polyphonic triggering.
- **Granular Player** retrieves a group of neighboring slices and plays grains based on defined length and offset, with playback probability introducing variation. Though less flexible than traditional granular synths, it offers stable, timbre-focused granulation.
- **Morph Player** loops a group of nearby slices, scaling amplitude by proximity. The result is a fluid, evolving texture that moves through adjacent timbral zones—ideal for small corpora with high perceptual continuity.

Together, these clients illustrate that *Mosaïque* is more than a sampler—it is a compositional environment. Its architecture enables real-time orchestration of sound through diverse playback logics, transforming corpus material into an expressive, interactive space for creation and performance.

4 Discussion

4.1 Balancing Technique and Concept

While *Mosaïque* offers immediate creative potential, we have noted the risk of prioritizing technical novelty over conceptual depth. Like many tech-driven tools, it can encourage works that showcase the tool rather than convey a meaningful artistic idea. This reflects a broader tension in music technology: balancing expressive capability with artistic intention. *Mosaïque's* responsiveness invites playful exploration, but the composer's challenge remains to situate that exploration within a clear aesthetic or critical framework. This mirrors ongoing discussions in computational creativity about the necessity of embedding generative systems within artistically meaningful contexts (McCormack et al., 2019).

4.2 Composition, spatiality, and the role of the interface

Mosaïque's ability to re-orchestrate sound corpora in real time shapes compositional thinking—not just through timbre, but through a spatial paradigm. Rather than sequencing in time, artists navigate a sonic landscape, fostering non-linear, embodied engagement well-suited to improvisation and

hybrid practices.

This often results in a “comprovisational” approach: a curated sonic environment is prepared in advance, but real-time interaction drives the unfolding form. The interface becomes more than a control surface—it acts as a responsive partner, like an ensemble or instrument, through which narrative and structure emerge.

Rather than being predetermined, musical form arises from movement through sound space. This produces outcomes that are unpredictable yet coherent, allowing composition and improvisation to merge in a generative, exploratory practice.

4.3 Instrumentality and reduced listening

A key idea emerges from using Mosaïque, which is the creation of multiple virtual instruments through learned navigation of different corpora. Each corpus—whether composed of instrumental, vocal, electronic, or environmental sounds—demands a unique approach. Over time, users develop idiomatic gestures and sonic fluency, treating each corpus as a distinct instrument.

Rather than triggering static events, Mosaïque invites musicians to shape sound in real time, developing a responsive, embodied relationship with timbre and texture. This shift echoes Pierre Schaeffer’s concept of *écoute réduite*, where attention is focused on the sound itself—its shape, motion, and spectral detail—rather than its source or meaning.

Navigating timbre space requires this kind of perceptual focus. Users learn to recognize and manipulate sonic fragments based on qualitative traits like envelope or spectral content, gradually transforming their corpus into a terrain of expressive potential. In this sense, Mosaïque becomes an ecosystem of virtual instruments. Learning the software involves not just technical skill but cultivating an intuitive ear and a spatial understanding of sound morphology—an instrumentalization through listening.

4.4 Accessibility, embodied knowledge, and constraints

Mosaïque is designed for accessibility—no programming is required, and its integration into Ableton Live allows musicians to engage directly with advanced synthesis techniques through gesture, space, and feedback. This ease of use supports embodied interaction, enabling artists from non-technical backgrounds to explore CBCS intuitively. We acknowledge that integrating Mosaïque within Ableton Live limits accessibility to users with a paid license for the platform. However, we are currently working on developing a free and open-source standalone version of the instrument.

The system is not without limitations. Large corpora can lead to slow loading times or indexing delays, which may disrupt creative flow for new users. To address this, Mosaïque provides visual feedback and encourages strategies like segmenting corpora or using curated subsets. These constraints, while initially challenging, can become creatively productive, prompting users to focus their material and develop refined navigation strategies.

In balancing ease of access with inherent technical limitations, Mosaïque fosters both immediate engagement and deeper learning—grounding advanced processes in intuitive, exploratory practice.

5 Conclusion

Multiple tools exist for music creation with the technique of CBCS. The development of Mosaïque has however helped us understand how CBCS can reshape musical tools, gestures, and thinking. By centering dimensionality reduction, audio descriptors, and spatial navigation, this approach invites emergent forms where musicians listen, respond, and organize sound in real time.

Rather than a finished method, Mosaïque offers an entry point into deeper artistic questions: How do different descriptor spaces shape expression? How might interfaces promote collaboration and embodiment? And what if corpus curation itself becomes a collective compositional act?

Concatenative synthesis, then, is more than a technique—it is a paradigm for reimagining musical creation. The tools are here; what remains is to keep listening, experimenting, and composing through the corpus.

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References

- Bell, J. (2023, May). Maps as Scores: "Timbre Space" Representations in Corpus-Based Concatenative Synthesis. *International Conference on Technologies for Music Notation and Representation (TENOR)*. <https://hal.science/hal-04182706>
- Bernardes, G., Guedes, C., & Pennycook, B. (2013). EarGram: An Application for Interactive Exploration of Concatenative Sound Synthesis in Pure Data. In M. Aramaki, M. Barthet, R. Kronland-Martinet, & S. Ystad (Eds.), *From Sounds to Music and Emotions* (pp. 110–129). Springer. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-41248-6_7
- Bevilacqua, F., Boyer, E. O., Françoise, J., Houix, O., Susini, P., Roby-Brami, A., Hanneton, S., De Peralta Menendez, & Lotze, M. (2016, August 25). *Sensori-Motor Learning with Movement Sonification: Perspectives from Recent Interdisciplinary Studies*. | *EBSCOhost*. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fnins.2016.00385>
- Chapman, O., & Sawchuk, K. (2015). Creation-as-Research: Critical Making in Complex Environments. *RACAR: Revue d'art Canadienne / Canadian Art Review*, 40(1), 49–52.
- Constanzo, R. (2022). *SP-Tools – Machine Learning Tools for Drums and Percussion « Rodrigo Constanzo* [Computer software]. <https://rodrigoconstanzo.com/sp-tools/>
- Demers, J. T. (2010). *Listening through the noise: The aesthetics of experimental electronic music*. Oxford University Press.
- Einbond, A., Schwarz, D., Borghesi, R., & Schnell, N. (2016). *Introducing CatOracle: Corpus-based Concatenative Improvisation with the Audio Oracle Algorithm*. 515—519.
- Fiebrink, R., & Sonami, L. (2020, July 21). *Reflections on Eight Years of Instrument Creation with Machine Learning*. International Conference on New Interfaces for Musical Expression (NIME), Birmingham, UK. <https://nime2020.bcu.ac.uk/>

- Garber, L., & Ciccola, T. (2021). *AudioStellar* [Computer software]. MUNTREF Centro de Arte y Ciencia.
- Ghisi, D. (2017). *Music across music: Towards a corpus-based, interactive computer-aided composition* [Phdthesis, Université Pierre et Marie Curie - Paris VI].
<https://theses.hal.science/tel-01880061>
- Joachim Gossmann, & Max Neupert. (2014). *Musical Interface to Audiovisual Corpora of Arbitrary Instruments*. 151–154.
- Jordà, S. (2005). *Digital Lutherie Crafting musical computers for new musics; performance and improvisation* [Universitat Pompeu Fabra]. <http://hdl.handle.net/10803/575372>
- Leman, M. (2012). Musical gestures and embodied cognition. *Journées d'Informatique Musicale*.
<https://hal.science/hal-03041745>
- Ma, B., Sargen, E., Roure, D. D., & Howard, E. (2024). Learning to Learn: A Reflexive Case Study of PRiSM SampleRNN. *AIMC 2024 (09/09 - 11/09)*.
<https://aimc2024.pubpub.org/pub/fnpykfdv/release/1>
- Manovich, L. (2018). *AI aesthetics*. Strelka Press Moscow.
- McCormack, J., Gifford, T., & Hutchings, P. (2019). *Autonomy, Authenticity, Authorship and Intention in computer generated art* (No. arXiv:1903.02166). arXiv.
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1903.02166>
- Miranda, E. R., & Wanderley, M. (2006). *New Digital Musical Instruments: Control And Interaction Beyond the Keyboard (Computer Music and Digital Audio Series)*. A-R Editions, Inc.
- Piazza, D. (Director). (2025, March 13). *Topologies d'intrication* [Video recording]. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15881323>
- Roads, C. (2001). *Microsound*. <https://direct.mit.edu/books/monograph/3787/Microsound>
- Roma, G., Green, O., & Tremblay, P. A. (2019). *Adaptive Mapping of Sound Collections for Data-driven Musical Interfaces*. 313—318.
- Schaeffer, P. (1966). *Traité des objets musicaux*. Editions Du Seuil. Paris. France.

- Schwarz, D. (2006a). Concatenative sound synthesis: The early years. *Journal of New Music Research*, 35(1), 3—22. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09298210600696857>
- Schwarz, D. (2006b). *Real-time Corpus-based Concatenative Synthesis with CataRT*. 9th Int. Conference on Digital Audio Effects (DAFx-06).
- Schwarz, D. (2012). *The Sound Space as Musical Instrument: Playing Corpus-Based Concatenative Synthesis*. 250—253.
- Schwarz, D., Roebel, A., Yeh, C., & Laburthe, A. (2016). *Concatenative Sound Texture Synthesis Methods and Evaluation*. 217—224.
- Smalley, D. (1997). Spectromorphology: Explaining sound-shapes. *Organised Sound*, 2(2), 107—126.
- Thibault, D. (2024). Mosaique—Concatenative Synthesis Instrument for the Practicing Musicians. *AIMC 2024 (09/09 - 11/09)*. <https://aimc2024.pubpub.org/pub/buh7kcah/release/1>
- Thibault, D., & Catalão, J. (Directors). (2024, January 26). *Stella's Prophet* [Video recording]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15882341>
- Thibault, D., & Harvey, S. (Directors). (2024, January 26). *Navigating Calmer Oceans* [Video recording]. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15880778>
- Tremblay, P. A., Green, O., Roma, G., & Harker, A. (2019). *From Collections to Corpora: Exploring Sounds through Fluid Decomposition*. 223—228.
- Tremblay, P. A., Roma, G., & Green, O. (2021). Enabling Programmatic Data Mining as Musicking: The Fluid Corpus Manipulation Toolkit. *Computer Music Journal*, 45(2), 9—23. https://doi.org/10.1162/comj_a_00600
- Tremblay, P. A., & Schwarz, D. (2010). *Surfing the Waves: Live Audio Mosaicing of an Electric Bass Performance as a Corpus Browsing Interface*. NIME10.
- Truax, B. (1990). Composing with Real-Time Granular Sound. *Perspectives of New Music*, 28(2), 120—134. <https://doi.org/10.2307/833014>
- Zappi, V., & McPherson, A. (2014). *Dimensionality and Appropriation in Digital Musical Instrument Design*. 455—460. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1178993>

Zbyszyński, M., Di Donato, B., Visi, F. G., & Tanaka, A. (2021). Gesture-Timbre Space: Multidimensional Feature Mapping Using Machine Learning and Concatenative Synthesis. In R. Kronland-Martinet, S. Ystad, & M. Aramaki (Eds.), *Perception, Representations, Image, Sound, Music* (Vol. 12631). Springer.